

NanoSolveIT

Innovative Nanoinformatics models and tools: towards
a Solid, verified and Integrated Approach to Predictive (eco)Toxicology

Grant Agreement Number 814572

Deliverable Report 7.5

Deliverable	D7.5 NanoSolveIT standalone software application
Work Package:	WP7: Development of the NanoSolveIT e-Platform
Delivery date:	2023-08-31
Lead Beneficiary:	NovaM
Nature of Deliverable:	Demonstrator
Dissemination Level:	Public
Licence:	CC-BY 4.0 International (unless where differently specified)

Submitted by:	Harry Sarimveis, Pantelis Karatzas, Jason Sotiropoulos, (NTUA) Dimitra Danai Varsou, Konstantinos D. Papavasileiou, Panagiotis Kolokathis, Nikolaos Sidiropoulos, Maria Antoniou, Nikoletta-Maria Koutroumpa, Andreas Tsoumanis, Nikolaos Cheimarios, Antreas Afantitis (NovaM)
Revised by:	Dave Winkler(LTU), Mary Gulumian (NWU)
Approved by:	Iseult Lynch (UoB) and All consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 814572

Contents

Summary	3
List of Abbreviations	3
Introduction	4
1. Containerised applications	5
1.1 Containerisation	5
1.1.1 Checking if docker is installed in the local machine	6
1.1.2 Running a NanoSolveIT microservice on the local machine	8
1.1.3 Using the application	10
2. Containerised applications in enterprise environments	11
2.1 Kubernetes	11
2.1.1 Deploying the Vythos application on a local machine through Kubernetes	11
2.1.2 Deploying the NanoFASE application on a local machine through Kubernetes	16
2.1.2.1 Deployment of the NanoFASE API and the NanoFASE service	16
2.1.2.2 Deployment of the NanoFASE application	20
2.1.3 Deploying the Modelsbase application on a local machine through Kubernetes	23
2.1.3.1 The modelsbase database	28
2.1.4 Configuration of OpenID Connect server.	28
2.1.5 Deploying the NanoXtract application on a local machine through Kubernetes	29
2.1.6 Deploying the Multi-box aerosol application on a local machine through Kubernetes	33
2.1.7 Deploying the Lung exposure application on a local machine through Kubernetes	35
Appendix	40
List of available docker images of the NanoSolveIT applications	40

Summary

Deliverable 7.5 reports the development of a standalone version of the NanoSolveIT cloud platform. Throughout the project, a rigorous approach was taken to establish precise technical requirements for achieving the desired goals of an efficient, user-friendly, secure, sustainable, and scalable platform (e-platform) and infrastructure. One of the critical issues to be addressed in the development of the NanoSolveIT e-platform was ensuring sustainability of the microservices. To address this, the decision was made to package the microservices into Docker containers, effectively encapsulating all necessary system dependencies. By adopting Docker as the containerization tool, the development team ensured broad adaptability, extensive collaboration capabilities, and easy access to software packages through public repositories such as <https://hub.docker.com/>. In this deliverable report, we show how this technology not only facilitated rapid development of the NanoSolveIT cloud applications but also enabled the deployment of the services in standalone mode for users who prefer not to share their data to a Cloud.

Additionally, the report highlights the critical role of Kubernetes, the *de facto* platform for numerous open-source projects, as the container orchestration tool for the NanoSolveIT platform. Kubernetes further strengthened the capabilities of the standalone version. It offers unparalleled support and compatibility, allowing NanoSolveIT services to be deployed on any infrastructure running Kubernetes.

This deliverable report describes the development of the standalone software application, emphasising the microservice implementation, and the role of containerization. The resulting application demonstrates efficiency, sustainability, versatility, and compatibility with different computational environments.

Advantages of a standalone version of the cloud platform include:

1. *Flexibility*: users can deploy NanoSolveIT applications in different computational environments, such as on personal computers.
2. *Accessibility*: users can access the platform and its services without an internet connection.
3. *Security*: users have full control over their data and enhanced security, keeping sensitive information in their own infrastructure.
4. *Scalability*: the platform can be scaled according to the user's needs, and can be deployed on different hardware configurations without relying on external cloud resources.

List of Abbreviations

API - Application Programming Interface
AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway
DNS - Domain Name System
HTTP: HyperText Transfer Protocol
IATA - Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment
QSAR - Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
SSL - Secure Sockets Layer
TLS - Transport Layer Security
TCP - Transmission Control Protocol
URI - Uniform Resource Identifiers
URL - Uniform Resource Locator
VM - Virtual Machines
YAML - YAML Ain't Markup Language

Introduction

In the initial phase of the NanoSolveIT project, WP7 defined an extensive technical framework that ensured efficient development of services, seamless and secure integration, and long-term sustainability and scalability. A key aspect of this framework was the use of cutting-edge IT tools, including Docker and Kubernetes, which offer sustainability, flexibility, and effective management of various applications. The technical infrastructure outlined in detail in Deliverable 7.1 served as a reference, providing guidance and support for rapid development of diverse nanoinformatics tools as microservices, as described in detail in Deliverable 7.3.

The final version of the NanoSolveIT e-platform, described in Deliverable 7.4 and accessible at <https://cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>, incorporates over 35 distinct services covering all nanoinformatics operations. These services are grouped into seven categories and include (i) exposure models, (ii) deep learning and image analysis tools, (iii) predictive models (e.g., Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) / Read-across models), (iv) biokinetics models, (v) omics analysis, molecular pathways, Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) services, (vi) databases and data enrichment tools, and (vii) Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs).

This technical framework enables the deployment and use of the NanoSolveIT applications in standalone mode across various computational environments. These include standard personal computers and most operating systems. Within this deliverable, we provide detailed guidelines for NanoSolveIT users on how to independently deploy the platform's applications in standalone mode and install them on local servers. Our aim is to ensure that the instructions are clear and simple to follow to enable user autonomy. Consequently, several illustrative examples are provided to assist users with the process.

1. Containerised applications

1.1 Containerisation

As summarised in Deliverable 7.3, the NanoSolveIT project partners developed their services as Docker images that are deployed and run in containers on the NanoSolveIT e-platform. The NanoSolveIT Docker hub, accessible at <https://hub.docker.com/u/nanosolveit>, provides a list of Docker images (Figure 1) for the microservices developed.

Docker, and the developed tools, use freely available software. Docker Desktop (<https://www.docker.com/products/docker-desktop>) and docker Engine (<https://docs.docker.com/engine/>) can be installed on various infrastructures, including Virtual Machines (VMs), and on servers and personal computers, and are compatible with most operating systems. On Windows, a Windows installer manages all requirements, allowing docker to be installed and operated on VMs. Docker is also compatible with most Linux distributions (Ubuntu, Debian, etc.) and Apple computers. This ensures that the software can be executed on any infrastructure, maximising its utility for industry stakeholders and regulatory authorities. Docker website's official documentation provides detailed step-by-step installation guides tailored for various operating systems, including Windows, macOS, and several Linux distributions (<https://docs.docker.com/get-docker/>)

Deploying an application in standalone mode using these tools requires a basic understanding of networking¹, volume provisioning², and other technical aspects. In this deliverable, we provide an illustration of the fundamental commands that can be executed on any running Docker runtime to execute an application from the NanoSolveIT platform on a personal computer - A Docker runtime represents the environment where a Docker container runs, handling the container's resource management and guaranteeing its separation from other processes. Additionally, several commands are available to verify the availability and status of a Docker runtime on the user's computer.

For a comprehensive list of all the docker containers developed in the NanoSolveIT projects, please refer to the Appendix.

In the following subsections, the steps required to install, run and utilise the NanoSolveIT microservices on local machines are presented.

¹ Networking is the process of **connecting computing devices such that that can exchange data and share resources with each other**. These networked devices use a system of rules, called communications protocols, to transmit information over physical or wireless technologies.

² Dynamic volume provisioning allows storage volumes to be created on-demand. Without dynamic provisioning, cluster administrators have to manually make calls to their storage provider to create new storage volumes, and then create PersistentVolume objects to represent them in Kubernetes.

nanosolveit

Community Organization nanosolveit Joined April 15, 2020

Repositories

Displaying 1 to 18 repositories

nanosolveit/doxrelease · 6 · 0

By nanosolveit · Updated 14 days ago

Image

nanosolveit/doxviability · 3 · 0

By nanosolveit · Updated 14 days ago

Image

nanosolveit/deepsegm · 3 · 0

By nanosolveit · Updated 6 months ago

Image

nanosolveit/sem_segmentation · 8 · 0

By nanosolveit · Updated 8 months ago

Image

nanosolveit/viablecells · 23 · 0

By nanosolveit · Updated 8 months ago

Figure 1 : A screenshot of NanoSolveIT docker images hosted at the project's docker hub <https://hub.docker.com/u/nanosolveit> (as of August 2023). We note that this will continue to be extended beyond the project lifetime as new microservices are implemented.

1.1.1 Checking if docker is installed in the local machine

The command `< docker version >` will display relevant information from the installed runtime, if one is found. The response may vary depending on the specific setup and version of Docker installed, but will generally

include information on the client and server versions, and details such as build date and commit. The following is an example of a possible response to the command on a Unix operating system (Table 1) while Table 2 presents an example of a possible response on a Windows operating system.

Table 1. Docker version command and the response from a Unix operating system

```
% docker version

Client:
Version:          20.10.16
API version:      1.41
Go version:       go1.17.10
Git commit:       aa7e414
Built:            Thu May 12 09:17:28 2022
OS/Arch:          darwin/amd64
Context:          default

Server: Docker Desktop 4.8.2 (77141)
Engine:
Version:          20.10.16
API version:      1.41 (minimum version 1.12)
Go version:       go1.17.10
Git commit:       f756502
Built:            Thu May 12 09:15:33 2022
OS/Arch:          linux/amd64
Experimental:     false
containerd:
Version:          1.6.4
GitCommit:        212e8b6fa2f44b9c21b2798135fc6fb7c53efc16
runc:
Version:          1.1.1
GitCommit:        v1.1.1-0-g52de29d
docker-init:
Version:          0.19.0
GitCommit:        de40ad0
```

Table 2. Docker version command and the response from Windows operating system

```
% docker version

C:\Users\harri>docker version
Client:
Cloud integration: v1.0.29
Version:          20.10.22
API version:      1.41
Go version:       go1.18.9
Git commit:       3a2c30b
Built:            Thu Dec 15 22:36:18 2022
OS/Arch:          windows/amd64
Context:          default
```

```
Experimental:      true

Server: Docker Desktop 4.16.3 (96739)
Engine:
  Version:         20.10.22
  API version:     1.41 (minimum version 1.12)
  Go version:      go1.18.9
  Git commit:      42c8b31
  Built:           Thu Dec 15 22:26:14 2022
  OS/Arch:         linux/amd64
  Experimental:    false
containerd:
  Version:         1.6.14
  GitCommit:       9ba4b250366a5ddde94bb7c9d1def331423aa323
runc:
  Version:         1.1.4
  GitCommit:       v1.1.4-0-g5fd4c4d
docker-init:
  Version:         0.19.0
  GitCommit:       de40ad0
```

1.1.2 Running a NanoSolveIT microservice on the local machine

Once the container runtime is installed and accessible on the computer, applications developed for NanoSolveIT can be deployed. The commands to run a Docker depend on the specific parameters required for the application running inside the container and the host computer. In Table 3 below, we present the basic command that can be used to run a NanoSolveIT service on a personal computer.

Table 3. Docker command to run a NanoSolveIT application, where [OPTION] is selected from the list of available Docker images As shown in Table 4 for a specific application.

```
Reference command:

docker run [OPTIONS] IMAGE [COMMAND] [ARG...]
```

Some common options for the `docker run` command include:

- `-d`: Detached mode. This runs the container in the background.
- `--name`: Assigns a name to the container.
- `-p`: Maps a host port to a container port, e.g., `-p 8080:80`.
- `--rm`: Removes the container automatically once it's stopped.

For a comprehensive list and detailed explanations of all options available for the `docker run` command, the reader can consult the official Docker documentation at: <https://docs.docker.com/engine/reference/run/>.

For deployments in environments such as servers within a private network, it is advisable to consult local technical personnel for guidance and assistance.

We exemplify the process of running a NanoSolveIT application locally using the Vythos application, accessible at: <https://vythos.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>. The corresponding Docker image for Vythos is found at: <https://hub.docker.com/r/demetradanae/vythos>.

The following command runs the Vythos Docker image as a running container: `docker run -p 3838:3838 -d demetradanae/vythos` (Table 4).

Given that the majority of applications on NanoSolveIT are designed as microservices, they usually operate on ports that can be accessed via HTTP requests. For this specific application, port 3838 is designated to make the application accessible from the container, using the `-p` option.

Table 4. Docker command to run the Vythos NanoSolveIT application and the response if run on a Mac OS.

```
% docker run -p 3838:3838 -d demetradanae/vythos

response from terminal (if the command is executed from a mac os terminal)

latest: Pulling from demetradanae/vythos
146bd6a88618: Downloading [=====>]
17.9MB/45.38MB
77be22d2817d: Downloading [>]
3.777MB/205.7MB
aa186892bd6c: Downloading [=>]
3.765MB/100.5MB
f868b77d5a50: Waiting
f6db6a7f644b: Waiting
3e134c9c95df: Waiting
a561c0dc6587: Waiting
14ab526c72a9: Waiting
a06154021b48: Waiting
40810b8f55c5: Waiting
8e750485374d: Waiting
f6c05a436ef9: Waiting
c88e2e27a387: Waiting
8ad3be65e925: Waiting
```

Once the docker image is deployed, it is assigned a unique ID that is printed on the terminal. The running image can be identified as a running container using the command `docker ps` (Table 5).

Table 5. Docker command to display the running containers

```
% docker ps
CONTAINER ID   IMAGE                                COMMAND                                CREATED        STATUS
```

PORTS	NAMES			
b2e51cdc3a81	demetradae/vyθος	"/usr/bin/shiny-serv..."	1 hour ago	Up 1
hours	0.0.0.0:3838->3838/tcp	musng_colden		

1.1.3 Using the application

The application is now running on a personal computer, making it accessible and usable as a standalone application (Figure 2). The necessary data for the application to function will reside on the computer or the private network where the application is deployed.

Applications deployed on a personal computer can be accessed using the relevant port. Here, the application runs on port 3838. To access it, the localhost or a similar IP address in a web browser can be used. Since this application has a user interface, it can be conveniently accessed through a web browser.

Figure 2: Using the Vythos application locally through a web browser at localhost:3838.

2. Containerised applications in enterprise environments

2.1 Kubernetes

In Deliverable 7.1, a comprehensive and detailed evaluation was conducted to compare different ecosystems for optimising and automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications. After careful analysis, Kubernetes was selected as the most suitable platform for orchestrating the NanoSolveIT microservices. One of the key factors for choosing Kubernetes was its cloud-agnostic nature, as it does not have native integrations with any specific cloud provider, providing flexibility in selecting the hosting infrastructure. Kubernetes automatically restarts failed containers, replaces containers, terminates unresponsive containers based on user-defined health checks, and ensures that containers are not advertised to clients until they are ready to serve.

Deploying an application on Kubernetes requires a running instance to be established. Multiple solutions exist for deploying Kubernetes instances. The official guide is accessible at: <https://kubernetes.io/docs/setup/>.

The NanoSolveIT Kubernetes cluster offers functionalities such as service discovery, load balancing, network distribution, and automated rollouts and rollbacks. The cluster is composed of multiple components working together, including Deployments, Pods, Replica Sets, Services, and Ingresses. These components are declared using configuration files written in the YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML), which is a data serialisation language commonly used in Kubernetes. The YAML files required to deploy the NanoSolveIT platform on a Kubernetes infrastructure are available in the NanoSolveIT GitHub repository: <https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform->

Each infrastructure can consist of various resources. The scripts provided in the NanoSolveIT GitHub repository have been tested and deployed on a simple BareMetal infrastructure with the appropriate networking configuration. These scripts can be used to deploy the entire NanoSolveIT infrastructure on any Kubernetes environment with the necessary modifications to the deployment scripts. Basic knowledge of Kubernetes and networking is required to make the necessary changes to the YAML files and to successfully run the NanoSolveIT platform in different environments.

The YAML files represent the minimum requirements for Kubernetes and can be applied to both public and private infrastructures. The main differences are related to networking configurations and file system provisioning.

The NanoSolveIT cloud platform can be accessed through the domain "*.cloud.nanosolveit.eu". However, to adapt the scripts to specific environments, changes need to be made to the services and ingress deployments. By adjusting the networking and other relevant parameters in the provided scripts, the NanoSolveIT applications can be deployed and accessed in various environments.

To demonstrate the process of deploying a NanoSolveIT application through Kubernetes, we have selected the three applications, presented below.

2.1.1 Deploying the Vythos application on a local machine through Kubernetes

The Vythos cloud application can be accessed at: <https://vythos.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>. The corresponding docker file is available at: <https://hub.docker.com/r/demetradanae/vythos>

The YAML files for the Vythos applications are accessible at:

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform/blob/main/Yamls/ShinyApps/vythos.yaml>

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform/blob/main/Yamls/ShinyApps/vythosingress.yaml>

To deploy the Vythos application on a local machine, a kubernetes namespace is required first. This can be provided either through a YAML file or as a kubectl command (Table 6).

Table 6. The kubectl command to create a namespace for Vythos on kubernetes.

```
> kubectl create ns vythos
```

Next, the `kubectl apply` command is used twice to deploy the Vythos application and the corresponding ingress (Table 7). Kubernetes ingress is a collection of routing rules that govern how external users access services running in a Kubernetes cluster

Table 7. The kubectl command for the deployment of the Vythos application and the corresponding ingress on a kubernetes cluster.

```
> kubectl apply -f vythos.yaml
> kubectl apply -f vythosingress.yaml
```

T

The YAML file for the Vythos application is presented in Table 8 below:

Table 8. YAML file for the deployment of the Vythos application

```
---
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: vythos-service
  namespace: shiny-apps
spec:
  type: NodePort
  selector:
    app: vythos-app
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 3838
    targetPort: 3838
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: vythos-app
  namespace: shiny-apps
```

```
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: vythos-app
  replicas: 1
  template:
    metadata:
      name: vythos-app
      labels:
        app: vythos-app
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: vythos-app
        image: demetradanae/vythos
        imagePullPolicy: Always
        ports:
        - containerPort: 3838
          name: vythos
```

The YAML file for deployment of the Vythos application service is exposed as a NodePort service listening on port 3838 and forwarding traffic to pods labelled as "vythos-app". The deployment ensures that one replica of the "vythos-app" pod template is running that uses the Docker image "demetradanae/vythos" and exposes port 3838 within the container. The information contained in the YAML file is described in more detail below:

1. Service:

- The **'kind'** field specifies that it is a Kubernetes service.
- The **'apiVersion'** field indicates the version of the Kubernetes application programming interface (API) being used.
- The **'metadata'** section provides information about the service.
 - The **'name'** field defines the name of the service as "vythos-service".
 - The **'namespace'** field specifies the namespace in which the service will be created, which is "shiny-apps".
- The **'spec'** section describes the specifications of the service.
 - The **'type'** field indicates that the service should be exposed as a NodePort service.
 - The **'selector'** field specifies the label selector to match the corresponding pods.
 - In this case, it matches pods with the label **'app'** set to "vythos-app".
 - The **'ports'** field defines the ports on which the service should listen.
 - It specifies a single port configuration:
 - The **'protocol'** field sets the protocol to c).
 - The **'port'** field sets the port number to 3838.
 - The **'targetPort'** field specifies the target port to which traffic should be forwarded, which is also 3838.

2. Deployment:

- The **'apiVersion'** field specifies the Kubernetes API version.
- The **'kind'** field indicates that it is a Kubernetes deployment.
- The **'metadata'** section provides information about the deployment.
 - The **'name'** field defines the name of the deployment as "vythos-app".

- The **'namespace'** field specifies the namespace in which the deployment will be created, which is "shiny-apps".
- The **'spec'** section describes the specifications of the deployment.
 - The **'selector'** field specifies the label selector to identify the pods controlled by this deployment. In this case, it matches pods with the label app set to "vythos-app".
 - The **'replicas'** field sets the desired number of replicas (pods) for the deployment, which is 1 in this case.
 - The **'template'** field defines the pod template used to create new pods.
 - The **'metadata'** section provides metadata for the pod template.
 - The **'name'** field defines the name of the pod template as "vythos-app".
 - The **'labels'** field assigns labels to the pod template.
 - In this case, it sets the **'app'** label to "vythos-app".
- The second **'spec'** section describes the specifications of the pod template.
 - The **'containers'** field defines the containers to run within the pods. In this case, there is a single container named "vythos-app".
 - The **'name'** field specifies the name of the container.
 - The **'image'** field specifies the Docker image to use for the container, which is "demetradanae/vythos".
 - The **'imagePullPolicy'** field determines when to pull the container image, set to "Always" to ensure the latest version.
 - The **'ports'** field defines the ports exposed by the container. It specifies a single port configuration:
 - The **'containerPort'** field sets the port number to 3838.
 - The name **'field'** assigns a name to the port, which is "vythos".

The YAML file for the Vythos ingress is presented in Table 9 below. Please note that it is tested and deployed on Kubernetes version 1.14. In subsequent Kubernetes versions the **apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1** should be altered to comply with the newest version requirements of the Kubernetes platform. Documentation about Kubernetes ingresses can be found at <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/services-networking/ingress/>.

Table 9. The Vythos application ingress configuration

```

apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: vythos-app-secure
  namespace: shiny-apps
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.allow-http: "true"
    certmanager.k8s.io/acme-http01-edit-in-place: "true"
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"
    cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"
    nginx.ingress.kubernetes.io/ssl-redirect: "false"
    ingress.kubernetes.io/ssl-redirect: "false"
spec:
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - vythos.cloud.nanosolveit.eu

```

```
secretName: vythos-app-cert
rules:
- host: vythos.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
  http:
    paths:
    - backend:
        serviceName: vythos-service
        servicePort: 3838
      path: /
```

The information contained in the YAML file is described in more detail below:

- The **'apiVersion'** specifies the version of the Ingress resource.
- The **'kind'** indicates that this is an Ingress resource.
- The **'metadata'** section provides information about the Ingress.
 - The **'name'** field specifies the name of the Ingress as "vythos-app-secure".
 - The **'namespace'** field specifies the namespace in which the Ingress is created, which is "shiny-apps".
 - The **'annotations'** section includes various annotations that provide additional configuration options for the Ingress.
 - **'kubernetes.io/ingress.allow-http: "true"'** allows HTTP traffic to be served by the Ingress.
 - **'certmanager.k8s.io/acme-http01-edit-in-place: "true"'** enables the ACME HTTP01 challenge solver for Let's Encrypt certificates.
 - **'kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"'** specifies the Ingress controller class to use (in this case, the Nginx Ingress controller).
 - **'cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"'** specifies the cluster issuer to use for obtaining the transport layer security (TLS) certificate.
 - **'nginx.ingress.kubernetes.io/ssl-redirect: "false"'** disables the secure sockets layer (SSL) redirection for the Nginx Ingress controller.
 - **'ingress.kubernetes.io/ssl-redirect: "false"'** disables SSL redirection for the Ingress resource itself.
- The **'spec'** section defines the specifications of the Ingress.
 - The **'tls'** field specifies the TLS configuration for the Ingress.
 - The **'hosts'** field specifies the domain name for which the TLS certificate should be obtained. In this case, it is set to **'vythos.cloud.nanosolveit.eu'**.
 - The **'secretName'** field specifies the name of the Secret resource that holds the TLS certificate, which is **'vythos-app-cert'**.
 - The **'rules'** field defines the routing rules for the Ingress.
 - The **'host'** field specifies the domain name for which the rule applies, which is **'vythos.cloud.nanosolveit.eu'**.
 - The **'http'** field defines the routing for HTTP traffic.
 - The **'paths'** field specifies the path-based routing rules.
 - The **'backend'** field specifies the backend service to which traffic should be forwarded.
 - The **'serviceName'** field specifies the name of the Service resource that the traffic should be forwarded to, which is vythos-service.
 - The **'servicePort'** field specifies the port

Note that the annotations section of the Ingress resource may vary based on the specific deployment requirements. In NanoSolveIT, nginx is utilised as the Ingress controller for handling ingresses on Kubernetes. However, it is important to realise that the ‘**ingress.class annotation**’ can be set to another class of ingresses such as Traefik or any other managed class offered by a cloud provider. This flexibility allows for the selection of an appropriate Ingress controller that aligns with the deployment's needs.

2.1.2 Deploying the NanoFASE application on a local machine through Kubernetes

The NanoFASE Water-Soil-Organism cloud application can be accessed at: <https://nanoface.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>. The corresponding Docker image for NanoFASE is at: <https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/nanofase>. The YAML files can be found at: <https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/tree/main/Yamls/nanofase>

2.1.2.1 Deployment of the NanoFASE API and the NanoFASE service

First, a kubernetes namespace is required. This can be provided either through a YAML file or as a kubectl command (Table 10).

Table 10. The command to create a namespace on kubernetes

```
> kubectl create ns nanofase
```

To deploy the NanoFASE API on Kubernetes the command to use is again a ‘kubectl apply’ command executed on the folder where the deployment YAML file named api_deployment.yaml is located (Table 11).

Table 11. The command to deploy the NanoFASE API on kubernetes

```
> kubectl apply -f api_deployment.yaml
```

The script actually consists of two deployments, one for the pod deployment and one for deployment for the API, as shown in Table 12.

Table 12. YAML file for the deployment of the NanoFASE API

```
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: nanofase-api
  namespace: nanofase
spec:
  selector:
    app: nanofase-api
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
```

```
    port: 5000
    targetPort: 5001
  apiVersion: apps/v1
  kind: Deployment
  metadata:
    name: nanofase-api
    namespace: nanofase
  spec:
    selector:
      matchLabels:
        app: nanofase-api
    replicas: 1
    template:
      metadata:
        name: nanofase-api
        labels:
          app: nanofase-api
      spec:
        containers:
          - name: nanofase-api
            image: nanosolveit/nanofase-api:1.0.5
            ports:
              - containerPort: 5001
            env:
              - name: MONGO_URI
                value: "mongodb://mongodb-service.dbs:27017"
              - name: DATA_PATH
                value: "/nanofase-api/src/data"
              - name: MODEL_DATA
                value: "/nanofase-api/src/data/model/data/constants/thames_tio2_2015/"
              - name: MODEL_VARS
                value: "/nanofase-api/src/data/model/data/model_vars.yaml"
              - name: MODEL_CONFIG
                value: "/nanofase-api/src/data/config.nml"
              - name: MODEL_PATH
                value: "/nanofase/bin/main"
            volumeMounts:
              - name: workdir
                mountPath: /nanofase-api/conf
        initContainers:
          - name: config-data
            image: busybox
            command: ["sh", "-c", "echo \"{\\"web\\": { \\"issuer\\":
\\\"https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit\\\", \\"auth_uri\\\":
\\\"https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit/protocol/openid-
connect/auth\\\", \\"client_id\\\": \\"nanofase-api\\\", \\"client_secret\\\":
\\\"346179e8-ed0f-495e-8073-144c00e78c92\\\", \\"redirect_uris\\\": [
\\\"https://nanofaseapi.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/*\\\" ], \\"userinfo_uri\\\":
\\\"https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit/protocol/openid-
connect/userinfo\\\", \\"token_uri\\\":
\\\"https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit/protocol/openid-
```

```
connect/token\\", \\\"token_introspection_uri\\\":  
\\\"https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit/protocol/openid-  
connect/token/introspect\\\" } }\" > /work-dir/client_s.json"]  
  volumeMounts:  
  - name: workdir  
    mountPath: "/work-dir"  
  volumes:  
  - name: workdir  
    emptyDir: {}  
---
```

The content of the YAML file is similar to the one used in the corresponding YAML files of the Vythos application. There are three main differences:

- Definition of the main variables configuring the application using the env flag: Among these variables, the most critical one is **'MONGO_URI'**. The application relies on a MongoDB database for its runtime operations, as the data generated by the application requires substantial storage space. MongoDB serves as the storage and management service for all functionalities within the application. Other flags such as **'DATA_PATH'**, **'MODEL_DATA'**, **'MODEL_VARS'**, **'MODEL_CONFIG'**, and **'MODEL_PATH'** are application-specific and typically remain constant throughout the application's lifecycle.
- Use of init container, which serves as a configuration container: An init container is deployed alongside the main application container. Its primary function is to set up the appropriate environment and configure the application with properties that may be required and created / changed dynamically. For the deployment of the NanoFASE API we used this technique to modify the configuration of the authentication service. This approach is particularly useful when configuring a front-end application that is typically served from static compiled files.
- Inclusion of an authorisation service. The NanoFASE applications uses the OpenID Connect auth service which is an authentication service that can be integrated by multiple applications sharing the same authentication credentials and users. It can serve as the auth service in any environment in public and private cloud infrastructures. Multiple implementations of the OpenID connect servers are available. In the authentication service the following properties are defined:
 - **'issuer'**: The server endpoint that manages the authentication of the services.
 - **'auth_uri'**: The endpoint for initiating the authentication process.
 - **'client_id'**: The unique identifier for the client, configured on the authentication service.
 - **'client_secret'**: A confidential string configured on the authentication service, which is used to authenticate the client.
 - **'redirect_uris'**: The list of *Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI)* to which the authentication server can redirect the user after authentication.
 - **'userinfo_uri'**: The endpoint URI for retrieving user information.
 - **'token_uri'**: The endpoint for exchanging an authorization grant for an access token.
 - **'token_introspection_uri'**: The endpoint for introspecting the access token.

The above variables are configurable. In a standalone environment, these variables should be configured to match the corresponding DNS where the services are deployed. For instance, the value <https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu> should be changed to the appropriate DNS of the standalone service. This could be an IP address or any domain that satisfies the installation requirements. It could be a personal computer or a server accessible through an intranet, for example.

When the deployment of the NanoFASE API is completed, an ingress can be deployed to make the application accessible through a DNS. This means the application will be accessible through the local network and will respond through a DNS record. This is something that suits infrastructures like intranet, for example, where local DNS servers have been deployed. Like before, a ‘kubectly apply’ command is executed on the folder where the corresponding YAML file named `api_ingress.yaml` is located (Table 13).

Table 13. The command to deploy the ingress on the kubernetes cluster

```
kubectly apply -f api_ingress.yaml
```

The full YAML file is presented in Table 14.

Table 14. The NanoFASE API ingress configuration

```
apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: nanofase-api-secure
  namespace: nanofase
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"
    cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"
spec:
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - nanofaseapi.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    secretName: nanofase-api-cert
  rules:
  - host: nanofaseapi.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    http:
      paths:
      - backend:
          serviceName: nanofase-api
          servicePort: 5000
        path: /
```

As with the Vythos application, the variables specific to the NanoSolveIT cloud platform are integral components of this service. For a standalone deployment, these should be replaced by the variables relevant to the specific installation. Furthermore, variables such as `extensions/v1beta1` may change in the future for newer versions of the Kubernetes platform. Although these changes do occur, updates to these YAML files are relatively simple, ensuring they remain deployable and adaptable to future modifications of the Kubernetes API. The NanoSolveIT consortium is committed to providing the necessary support for the deployment and updating of these YAML files as required. The files will continue to be available on GitHub, accessible to all.

Once the application is deployed, the API and the Swagger documentation of the API can be accessed via the domain indicated in the ingress YAML file. Other services provided by Kubernetes, such as port services, can

facilitate access to the application from any computer, even in the absence of a domain name server within the infrastructure. Consequently, the API can be accessed through a browser as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Accessing the NanoFASE API locally from a browser

2.1.2.2 Deployment of the NanoFASE application

Once the API is deployed, it is skinned (aligned visually) with the user interface, making it readily accessible and facilitating access to the NanoFASE application. As with the API deployment, the NanoFASE deployment requires a service to render the pod accessible to the Kubernetes cluster network, and an ingress to allow the application to be accessed through a DNS. The 'kubectl apply' command is utilised on the corresponding YAML files, specifically app_deployment.yaml and app_ingress.yaml, as depicted in Table 15.

Table 15. The command for the deployment of the NanoFASE application and the ingress on a kubernetes cluster

```
> kubectl apply -f app_deployment.yaml
> kubectl apply -f app_ingress.yaml
```

T

The two YAML files are presented in Tables 16 and 17 below:

Table 16. YAML file for the deployment of the NanoFASE application

```
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: nanofase-app
  namespace: nanofase
```

```

spec:
  selector:
    app: nanofase-app
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 80
    targetPort: 80
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Pod
metadata:
  name: nanofase-app
  namespace: nanofase
  labels:
    app: nanofase-app
spec:
  containers:
  - name: nanofase-app
    image: nanosolveit/nanofase:1.0.7
    ports:
    - containerPort: 80
    volumeMounts:
    - name: workdir
      mountPath: /usr/share/nginx/html/conf
  initContainers:
  - name: config-data
    image: busybox
    command: ["sh", "-c", "echo \"${\\\"nanoFaseApi\\\"}:
\\\\\"https://nanofaseapi.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/\\\\\",\\\"stsServer\\\\\":
\\\\\"https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit\\\\\",\\\"redirect_url\\\\\" :
\\\\\"https://nanofase.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/\\\\\",\\\"client_id\\\\\":\\\"nanofase-
app\\\\\",\\\"response_type\\\\\" : \\\"id_token token\\\\\",\\\"scope\\\\\": \\\"openid email
profile\\\\\",\\\"silent_redirect_url\\\\\" :
\\\\\"https://nanofase.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/assets/silent-renew.html\\\\\"}\" > /work-
dir/conf.json" ]
    volumeMounts:
    - name: workdir
      mountPath: "/work-dir"
  dnsPolicy: Default
  volumes:
  - name: workdir
    emptyDir: {}
---

```

The YAML file for the deployment of the NanoFASE application indeed includes configurations for integration with an OpenID Connect authentication server. The detailed explanations for each of the variables are provided below:

- **'nanoFaseApi'**: This is the URL of the NanoFASE API. It serves as the base endpoint for all interactions with the NanoFASE application.
- **'stsServer'**: This refers to the URL of the OpenID Connect server with the realm that the client is registered to. It is responsible for providing authentication and issuing tokens.

- **'redirect_url'**: This is the URL where the application will be redirected after successful authentication, as dictated by the authentication protocol.
- **'client_id'**: This is the unique identifier for the client application registered in the OpenID Connect server.
- **'response_type'**: This indicates the type of response expected after authentication. Common values are 'code', 'id_token', 'token', or combinations of these.
- **'scope'**: This represents the extent of permissions that the client is requesting from the OpenID provider. Common scopes are 'openid', 'profile', 'email', etc.
- **'silent_redirect_url'**: This is the endpoint to which the OpenID provider will send the response for silent refresh of the ID token, a process used to renew a user's session without requiring explicit login again.

Table 17. The NanoFASE application ingress configuration

```
apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: nanofase-app-secure
  namespace: nanofase
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"
    cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"
spec:
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - nanofase.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    secretName: nanofase-app-cert
  rules:
  - host: nanofase.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    http:
      paths:
      - backend:
          serviceName: nanofase-app
          servicePort: 80
        path: /
```

As with the Vythos application, nginx is employed as the Ingress controller in Kubernetes for managing incoming network traffic, or ingresses.

Upon successful deployment of the application, it can be accessed via an ingress or another service that facilitates network accessibility. Networks could range from a network of a single application to an intranet serving an entire organisation. Once the application and its related services are deployed using the appropriate Kubernetes commands, the application can be accessed through a browser by any authorised user, without requiring an internet connection (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Accessing the NanoFASE application locally from a browser.

2.1.3 Deploying the Modelsbase application on a local machine through Kubernetes

Modelsbase is an application consisting of multiple microservices and microapps that integrate with the modelsbase API. The YAML files used to deploy Modelsbase can be found at the GitHub URL: <https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/tree/main/Yamls/modelsbase>.

The commands for the deployment of the Modelsbase application on a kubernetes cluster are shown in Table 18 below.

Table 18. The commands for the deployment of the modelsbase and the ingress on a kubernetes cluster

```
> kubectl apply -f oidcsec.yaml
> kubectl apply -f deployments.yaml
> kubectl apply -f python-gen-1.yaml
> kubectl apply -f api-ingress.yaml
```

The main file, deployments.yaml (Table 19) deploys a minimum set of pods and images necessary for the operation of Modelsbase.

Table 19. The YAML file to deploy the modelsbase application on a kubernetes cluster

```
kind: Service
```

```
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-python-generic-service
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    app: jaqpot-python-generic
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 8002
    targetPort: 8002
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-python-generic
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: jaqpot-python-generic
  replicas: 1
  template:
    metadata:
      name: jaqpot-python-generic
      labels:
        app: jaqpot-python-generic
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: jaqpot-python-generic
        image: euclia/jaqpot-python-generic
        ports:
        - containerPort: 8002
---
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-validation-service
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    app: jaqpot-validation
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 5000
    targetPort: 5000
---
apiVersion: apps/v1 # for versions before 1.8.0 use apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-validation-deployment
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: jaqpot-validation
  replicas: 1 # tells deployment to run 2 pods matching the template
  template: # create pods using pod definition in this template
    metadata:
```

```
    name: jaqpot-validation
    labels:
      app: jaqpot-validation
  spec:
    containers:
      - name: jaqpot-validation
        image: euclia/jaqpot-validation
        ports:
          - containerPort: 5000
---
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-r-generic-service
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    app: jaqpot-r-generic
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8004
      targetPort: 8004
---
apiVersion: apps/v1 # for versions before 1.8.0 use apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-r-generic-deployment
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: jaqpot-r-generic
  replicas: 1 # tells deployment to run 2 pods matching the template
  template: # create pods using pod definition in this template
    metadata:
      name: jaqpot-r-generic
      labels:
        app: jaqpot-r-generic
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: jaqpot-r-generic
          image: euclia/jpdi-r
          ports:
            - containerPort: 8004
---
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-api-service
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    app: jaqpot-api
  ports:
    - protocol: TCP
      port: 8080
      targetPort: 8080
---
kind: Service
```

```
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-api-exposed
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  type: NodePort
  selector:
    app: jaqpot-api
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 8080
    targetPort: 8080
    nodePort: 30180
---
apiVersion: apps/v1 # for versions before 1.8.0 use apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: jaqpot-api-deployment
  namespace: modelsbase
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: jaqpot-api
  replicas: 1 # tells deployment to run 2 pods matching the template
  template: # create pods using pod definition in this template
    metadata:
      name: jaqpot-api
      namespace: modelsbase
      labels:
        app: jaqpot-api
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: jaqpot-api
        image: nanosolveit/modelsbase-api:latest
        ports:
        - containerPort: 8080
        env:
          - name: JAQPOT_BASE_SERVICE
            value: https://modelsbase.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/modelsbase/services/
          - name: JAQPOT_LOCAL_IP
            value: http://78.108.37.109:30180
          - name: JAQPOT_SCHEMA
            value: https
          - name: JAQPOT_HOST
            value: modelsbase.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
          - name: JAQPOT_PORT
            value: '443'
          - name: JAQPOT_BASE
            value: /jaqpot/services
          - name: JAQPOT_CORS_ALLOWORIGIN
            value: '*'
          - name: JAQPOT_DB_HOST
            value: mongodb-service.dbs
          - name: JAQPOT_DB_PORT
            value: '27017'
          - name: JAQPOT_DB_NAME
            value: modelsbase
          - name: JAQPOT_BASE_VALIDATION
            value: "http://jaqpot-validation-service.jaqpot:5000/pws/validation"
```

```
- name: OIDC_ISSUER
  value: "https://login.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/auth/realms/nanosolveit/"
- name: OIDC_CLIENT_ID
  valueFrom:
    secretKeyRef:
      name: oidc-secret
      key: clientid
- name: OIDC_CLIENT_PASS
  valueFrom:
    secretKeyRef:
      name: oidc-secret
      key: secret
- name: OIDC_PROVIDER_CONF
  value: ".well-known/openid-configuration"
```

The environment variables that configures the modelsbase application are:

JAQPOT_BASE_SERVICE: the service (URL) that points to the modelsbase API.

JAQPOT_LOCAL_IP: the local IP address for modelsbase. This doesn't have to be correct since it is used for an irrelevant functionality of modelsbase.

JAQPOT_SCHEMA: the schema (http / https) that exposes the modelsbase API.

JAQPOT_HOST: the base URL that points to modelsbase API.

JAQPOT_PORT: the port that exposes modelsbase API (80 for plain http / 443 for https). This is used for the configuration of swagger user interface that documents the modelsbase API.

JAQPOT_BASE: the base URL for the modelsbase API.

JAQPOT_CORS_ALLOWORIGIN: enable or disable CORS for the API.

JAQPOT_DB_HOST: the database service.

JAQPOT_DB_PORT: the database port.

JAQPOT_DB_NAME: the name of the database (modelsbase uses mongodb as a database).

JAQPOT_BASE_VALIDATION: the service that exposes the validation service ([jaqpot-validation-service](#)).

OIDC_ISSUER: the open id connect server service

OIDC_CLIENT_ID: this is the client id that connects to the oidc server. This value is passed here through a kubernetes secret. This can be passed directly as string

OIDC_CLIENT_PASS: this is the password for integration with the oidc server.

OIDC_PROVIDER_CONF: this is the configuration url for the oidc service. (Well known open id connect endpoints).

After the successful deployment of the Modelsbase application, a particular application available through Modelsbase can be deployed using the commands shown in Table 20.

Table 20. The commands for the deployment of a specific application and ingress through modelsbase

```
> kubectl apply -f < the corresponding application yaml file >
> kubectl apply -f < the corresponding application ingress file >
```

For example the YAML files for the cytotox and the nanopot applications are available at:

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/tree/main/Yamls/cytotox>

and

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/tree/main/Yamls/nanopot>

2.1.3.1 The modelsbase database

Modelsbase requires a MongoDB database for its operations. MongoDB offers various deployment methods and detailed documentation is available online at:

<https://www.mongodb.com/docs/kubernetes-operator/stable/deploy/>.

When an instance of a MongoDB database is operational, the Modelsbase database can be restored. This procedure gives the API access to models deployed on the NanoSolveIT platform, making them available to users in the standalone version. The modelsbase database is compressed into a .tar.gz file and is retrievable via a GitHub URL as outlined in the YAML files for the Modelsbase deployment.

The database file is located at:

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/blob/main/Yamls/modelsbase/modelsbase.tar.gz>.

Once this file has been downloaded and appropriate access has been secured, the database can be deployed to a running MongoDB instance with the mongorestore command (Table 21). Detailed documentation of this command can be found at the official docs of MongoDB at <https://www.mongodb.com/docs/database-tools/mongorestore/>.

Table 21. The command for the deployment of the NanoSolveIT MongoDB instance

```
mongorestore --gzip --db "${DB_NAME_RESTORE}" ${BACKUP_FILE_GZ}/${DB_NAME}
```

DB_NAME_RESTORE is the name of the database that we wish to restore the db

BACKUP_FILE_GZ is the backup file and

DB_NAME is the database name which is <modelsbase> as also on the env variables of modelsbase.

2.1.4 Configuration of OpenID Connect server.

Many NanoSolveIT applications have been integrated with an OpenID Connect server, making use of the fundamental functionalities offered by these authentication services. For ease of integration in standalone environments, the configuration of the OpenID Connect server used in NanoSolveIT is provided in the standalone deployment GitHub repository at:

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/blob/main/Yamls/OIDC/realm-export.json>.

This configuration can be applied directly to a Keycloak OpenID Connect server (<https://www.keycloak.org/>), a containerised solution that can be deployed in any environment. By referencing the variables present in the realm-export.json file, the necessary clients for the application can be established on any OpenID Connect server.

2.1.5 Deploying the NanoXtract application on a local machine through Kubernetes

To deploy NanoXtract on a local machine, a kubernetes namespace is required first. This can be provided either through a YAML file or as a kubectl command (Table 22).

Table 22. The command to create a namespace for NanoXtract on kubernetes

```
> kubectl create ns nanoxtract
```

Next the kubectl apply command is used twice to deploy the NanoXtract application and the corresponding ingress (Table 23). Kubernetes ingress is a collection of routing rules that govern how external users access services running in a Kubernetes cluster.

Table 23. The command for the deployment of NanoXtract and the corresponding ingress on a kubernetes cluster

```
> kubectl apply -f nanoxtract.yaml
> kubectl apply -f nanoxtractingress.yaml
```

The YAML file for the NanoXtract application is presented in Table 24.

Table 24. The deployment of the NanoSolveIT NanoXtract application

```
---
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: nanoxtract-novanano-service
  namespace: novanano-apps
spec:
  selector:
    app: nanoxtract-novanano-app
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    name: http
    port: 80
    targetPort: 8080
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: nanoxtract-novanano-app
  namespace: novanano-apps
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: nanoxtract-novanano-app
  replicas: 1
  template:
    metadata:
      name: nanoxtract-novanano-app
      labels:
        app: nanoxtract-novanano-app
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: nanoxtract-novanano-app
        image: novamechanics/nanoxtract
        imagePullPolicy: Always
        ports:
```

```
- containerPort: 8080
  name: http
```

The deployment is similar to the Vythos example presented in Section 2.1.1. The YAML file for the deployment of the NanoXtract application service is exposed as a NodePort service listening on port 8080 and forwarding traffic to pods labelled as "nanoxtract-novanano-app". The deployment ensures that one replica of the "nanoxtract-novanano-app" pod template is running that uses the Docker image "novamechanics/nanoxtract" and exposes port 8080 within the container. The rest of the information follows the example of Vythos application in Section 2.1.1, however for the sake of completeness we add them also here:

The information contained in the YAML file are described in detail:

1. Service:

- The **'kind'** field specifies that it is a Kubernetes service.
- The **'apiVersion'** field indicates the version of the Kubernetes API being used.
- The **'metadata'** section provides information about the service.
 - The **'name'** field defines the name of the service as "nanoxtract-novanano-app". The **'namespace'** field specifies the namespace in which the service will be created, which is "novanano-apps".
- The **'spec'** section describes the specifications of the service.
 - The **'type'** field indicates that the service should be exposed as a NodePort service.
 - The **'selector'** field specifies the label selector to match the corresponding pods.
 - In this case, it matches pods with the label **'app'**.
 - The **'ports'** field defines the ports on which the service should listen.
 - It specifies a single port configuration:
 - The **'protocol'** field sets the protocol to TCP.
 - The **'port'** field sets the port number to 80.
 - The **'targetPort'** field specifies the target port to which traffic should be forwarded, which is also 8080.

2. Deployment:

- The **'apiVersion'** field specifies the Kubernetes API version.
- The **'kind'** field indicates that it is a Kubernetes deployment.
- The **'metadata'** section provides information about the deployment.
 - The **'name'** field defines the name of the deployment as "nanoxtract-novanano-app".
 - The **'namespace'** field specifies the namespace in which the deployment will be created, which is "novanano-apps".
- The **'spec'** section describes the specifications of the deployment.
 - The **'selector'** field specifies the label selector to identify the pods controlled by this deployment. In this case, it matches pods with the label app.
 - The **'replicas'** field sets the desired number of replicas (pods) for the deployment, which is 1 in this case.
 - The **'template'** field defines the pod template used to create new pods.
 - The **'metadata'** section provides metadata for the pod template.
 - The **'name'** field defines the name of the pod template as "nanoxtract-novanano-ap".
 - The **'labels'** field assigns labels to the pod template.

- In this case, it sets the **'app'** label to "nanoxtract-novanano-ap".
- The second **'spec'** section describes the specifications of the pod template.
 - The **'containers'** field defines the containers to run within the pods. In this case, there is a single container named "vythos-app".
 - The **'name'** field specifies the name of the container.
 - The **'image'** field specifies the Docker image to use for the container, which is "novamechanics/nanoxtract".
 - The **'imagePullPolicy'** field determines when to pull the container image, set to "Always" to ensure the latest version.
 - The **'ports'** field defines the ports exposed by the container. It specifies a single port configuration:
 - The **'containerPort'** field sets the port number to 8080.
 - The name **'field'** assigns a name to the port, which is "http".

As was the case in the NanoFASE API, when the deployment is completed an ingress can be deployed to make the application accessible through a DNS via the command shown in Table 25.

Table 25. The command to deploy the NanoXtract ingress on the kubernetes cluster

```
kubectl apply -f nanoxtractingress.yaml
```

The full YAML file of the NanoXtract API ingress is presented in Table 26.

Table 26. The NanoXtract API ingress configuration

```
apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: novanano11-app-secure
  namespace: novanano-apps
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"
    cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"
spec:
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - nanoxtract.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    secretName: nanoxtract-app-cert
  rules:
  - host: nanoxtract.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    http:
      paths:
      - backend:
          serviceName: nanoxtract-novanano-service
          servicePort: 8080
        path: /
```

Like in the Vythos application, the variables specific to the NanoSolveIT cloud platform are integral components of this service. For a standalone deployment, these should be replaced with the variables pertinent to the specific installation. Furthermore, variables such as `extensions/v1beta1` may change in the future due to new versions of the Kubernetes platform being released. Although these changes may occur over the coming years, updates to these YAML files are relatively simple, ensuring that they remain deployable and adaptable to future modifications of the Kubernetes API. The NanoSolveIT consortium is committed to providing the necessary support for the deployment and updating of these YAML files as required. The files will continue to be available on GitHub, accessible to all.

Once the application is deployed, the API and the Swagger documentation of the API can be accessed via the domain indicated in the ingress YAML file. Other services provided by Kubernetes, such as port services, can facilitate access to the application from any computer, even in the absence of a domain name server within the infrastructure. Consequently, the API can be accessed through a browser as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Accessing the NanoXtract API locally from a browser

2.1.6 Deploying the Multi-box aerosol application on a local machine through Kubernetes

As in the NanoXtract application, the Multi-box aerosol application can be accessed at <https://aerosol.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>. The corresponding Docker image for the multi-box aerosol can be found at <https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/aerosol>. The YAML files can be found at <https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/tree/main/Yamls/novanano>

To deploy the Multi-box aerosol application on a local machine, a Kubernetes namespace is required first. This can be provided either through a YAML file or as a `kubectl` command (Table 27).

Table 27. The command to create a namespace for the Multi-box aerosol application on Kubernetes

```
> kubectl create ns aerosol
```

Next the kubectl apply command is used twice to deploy the Multi-box aerosol application and the corresponding ingress (Table 28). Kubernetes ingress is a collection of routing rules that govern how external users access services running in a Kubernetes cluster.

Table 28. The command for the deployment of Multi-box aerosol and the corresponding ingress on a Kubernetes cluster.

```
> kubectl apply -f aerosolnovanano.yaml  
> kubectl apply -f aerosolnovananoingress.yaml
```

The YAML file for the Multi-box aerosol application is presented in Table 29.

Table 29. The deployment of the Multi-box aerosol application

```
---  
kind: Service  
apiVersion: v1  
metadata:  
  name: aerosol-novanano-service  
  namespace: novanano-apps  
spec:  
  selector:  
    app: aerosol-novanano-app  
  ports:  
  - protocol: TCP  
    name: http  
    port: 80  
    targetPort: 8080  
---  
apiVersion: apps/v1  
kind: Deployment  
metadata:  
  name: aerosol-novanano-app  
  namespace: novanano-apps  
spec:  
  selector:  
    matchLabels:  
      app: aerosol-novanano-app  
  replicas: 1  
  template:  
    metadata:  
      name: aerosol-novanano-app  
      labels:  
        app: aerosol-novanano-app  
    spec:  
      containers:  
      - name: aerosol-novanano-app  
        image: novamechanics/aerosol  
        imagePullPolicy: Always
```

```
ports:
- containerPort: 8080
  name: http
```

As was the case in the NanoFASE API, when the deployment is completed an ingress can be deployed to make the application accessible through a DNS via the command shown in Table 30.

Table 30. The command to deploy the ingress on the Kubernetes cluster

```
kubectl apply -f aerosolnovananoingress.yaml
```

The full YAML file is presented in Table 31.

Table 31. The Multi-box aerosol API ingress configuration

```
apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: novanano2-app-secure
  namespace: novanano-apps
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"
    cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"
spec:
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - aerosol.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    secretName: aerosol-app-cert
  rules:
  - host: aerosol.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    http:
      paths:
      - backend:
          serviceName: aerosol-novanano-service
          servicePort: 8080
        path: /
```

As with the NanoXtract application, the variables specific to the Multi-box aerosol application are integral components of this service. For a standalone deployment, these should be replaced with the variables pertinent to the specific installation. Furthermore, variables such as `extensions/v1beta1` may change in the future due to new versions of the Kubernetes platform. Although these changes may occur over the coming years, updates to these YAML files are relatively simple, ensuring they remain deployable and adaptable to future modifications of the Kubernetes API. The NanoSolveIT consortium is committed to providing the necessary support for the deployment and updating of these YAML files as required. The files will continue to be available on GitHub, accessible to all.

Once the application is deployed, the API and the Swagger documentation of the API can be accessed via the domain indicated in the ingress YAML file. Other services provided by Kubernetes, such as port services, can

facilitate access to the application from any computer, even in the absence of a domain name server within the infrastructure. Consequently, the API can be accessed through a browser as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Accessing the Multi-box aerosol API locally from a browser

2.1.7 Deploying the Lung exposure application on a local machine through Kubernetes

The Lung exposure cloud application can be accessed at <https://lungexposure.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/>. The corresponding Docker image for the multi-box aerosol can be found at <https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/lungexposure>.

The YAML files can be found at:

<https://github.com/nanosolveitcloud/NanoSolveITCloudPlatform-/tree/main/Yamls/novanano>

As with previous applications, to deploy the Lung exposure application on a local machine, a Kubernetes namespace is required first. This can be provided either through a YAML file or as a kubectl command (Table 32).

Table 32. The command to create a namespace for the Lung exposure application on Kubernetes.

```
> kubectl create ns lungexposure
```

Next the kubectl apply command is used twice to deploy the lung exposure application and the corresponding ingress (Table 33). Kubernetes ingress is a collection of routing rules that govern how external users access services running in a Kubernetes cluster.

Table 33. The command for the deployment of Lung exposure and the corresponding ingress on a Kubernetes cluster

```
> kubectl apply -f lungexposurenovanano.yaml
> kubectl apply -f lungexposurenovananoingress.yaml
```

Table 34. The deployment of the NanoSolveIT Lung exposure instance

```
---
kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: lungexp-novanano-service
  namespace: novanano-apps
spec:
  selector:
    app: lungexp-novanano-app
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    name: http
    port: 80
    targetPort: 8080
---
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: lungexp-novanano-app
  namespace: novanano-apps
spec:
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: lungexp-novanano-app
  replicas: 1
  template:
    metadata:
      name: lungexp-novanano-app
      labels:
        app: lungexp-novanano-app
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: lungexp-novanano-app
        image: novamechanics/lungexposure
        imagePullPolicy: Always
        ports:
        - containerPort: 8080
          name: http
```

As with the previous applications, when the deployment is completed an ingress can be created to make the application accessible through a DNS via the command shown in Table 35.

Table 35. The command to deploy the ingress on the kubernetes cluster

```
kubectl apply -f lungexposurenovananoingress.yaml
```

The full YAML file is presented in Table 36.

Table 36. The Lung exposure API ingress configuration

```
apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: novanano3-app-secure
  namespace: novanano-apps
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: "nginx"
    cert-manager.io/cluster-issuer: "letsencrypt-prod"
spec:
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - lungexposure.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    secretName: lungexposure-app-cert
  rules:
  - host: lungexposure.cloud.nanosolveit.eu
    http:
      paths:
      - backend:
          serviceName: lungexp-novanano-service
          servicePort: 8080
        path: /
```

Like in the NanoXtract application, the variables specific to Lung exposure are integral components of this service. For a standalone deployment, these should be replaced with the variables relevant to the specific installation. Furthermore, variables such as `extensions/v1beta1` may change in the future due to new versions of the Kubernetes platform. Although these changes may occur over the coming years, updates to these YAML files are relatively simple, ensuring they remain deployable and adaptable to future modifications of the Kubernetes API. The NanoSolveIT consortium is committed to providing the necessary support for the deployment and updating of these YAML files as required. The files will continue to be available on GitHub, accessible to all.

Once the application is deployed, the API and the Swagger documentation of the API can be accessed via the domain indicated in the ingress YAML file. Other services provided by Kubernetes, such as port services, can facilitate access to the application from any computer, even in the absence of a domain name server within the infrastructure. Consequently, the API can be accessed through a browser as shown in Figure 7.

Lung Exposure RESTful API ^{1.0.0}
 [Base URL: lungexposure.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/apis]
<https://lungexposure.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/apis/swagger.json>

NanoSolveIT RESTful APIs for Lung Exposure Dose Calculator

Schemes
 HTTPS

NanoSolveIT REST APIs

POST /restapi Returns a structure of three deposited doses

Models

Lung Exposure Response Data Structure >

Lung Exposure Input Data Structure >

VALID

Figure 7: Accessing the Lung exposure API locally from a browser

Following the pattern of previous applications, additional YAML files have been created for the following nine services:

<p>NInChI: InChI generation for NMs http://www.enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/nanocommons/NInChI/)</p>		
<p>Ecotox Model (Acute daphnia) https://ecotox.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/)</p>		
<p>Image nanodescriptors zeta-potential model</p>	<p>Simple4BoxNano: environmental fate</p>	<p>MS3bD zeta potential model https://mszeta.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/)</p>

3. Conclusions

Deliverable 7.5 summarises the successful development and deployment of NanoSolveIT services on a local scale, such as on a personal computer or local server. The use of Docker to package the microservices into containers has proven vital for maintaining the platform's adaptability and sustainability. This deliverable illustrates that this method of containerisation encapsulates all necessary system dependencies effectively, facilitating the platform's accessibility and ease of deployment in a standalone mode. Furthermore, we emphasised the important role of Kubernetes, the chosen container orchestration tool, in providing additional functionalities for running the NanoSolveIT services locally. As a universally acknowledged platform, Kubernetes has facilitated the deployment of NanoSolveIT services on any infrastructure equipped with Kubernetes.

Deploying the NanoSolveIT services on local machines offers numerous benefits. It brings flexibility by allowing users to deploy applications on a range of computational environments, thereby broadening the platform's reach. Accessibility is also significantly enhanced, with users now able to access the platform and its services without needing an internet connection, which maximises its availability. Furthermore, the standalone version promotes improved security, as users retain full control over their data and reduce reliance on external cloud resources.

Appendix

List of available docker images of the NanoSolveIT applications

For the deployment in standalone environments all of the NanoSolveIT applications are available as Docker images. These are available through the official Docker hub. Most of the applications are in an open source organisation, NanoSolveIT - <https://hub.docker.com/u/nanosolveit>. The others are available through the docker hub pages of the partners of the project.

Table 37. Docker image URLs for the applications and the corresponding port

Application Description	Partners involved in development	Docker image URL	port open for access
Multi-box aerosol occupational exposure model	NovaM, NRCWE	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/aerosol	8080
NanoFase WSO Environmental exposure model User Interface	NTUA, UKCEH	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/nanofase	80
NanoFase WSO Environmental exposure model API	NTUA, UKCEH	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/nanofase-api	5001
SimpleBox4Nano	NovaM, UKCEH	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/sb4n	8080
Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/cellviability	8080
Read-Across Model for Zeta Potential Prediction	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/zetapotential	8080
MS ³ bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/mszeta	8080
Vythos (Gold NM cell association, CNT absorption coefficients)	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/demetradanae/vythos	3838
NanoPot (logP, Zeta Potential in water, Cellular Uptake of A549 of Gold ENM)	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/nanopot	80
SAPNet: predict the toxicity of nanoparticle towards the CHO-K1 cell line	QSARLab	https://hub.docker.com/r/qsarlab/d/sapnets/	8050
Segmentation of nanoparticles from	NTUA, BAM	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/	7777

TEM images		veit/deepsegm	
Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Classification Model	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/cytotox	80
Model for zeta potential prediction	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/nanosolveit/zetapot	80
Facet Cytotoxicity Prediction: Metal oxide cytotoxicity prediction utilising facet-based electronic, and periodic table derived properties	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/facetcytotoxicity	8080
Ecotoxicological Read-Across Models for predicting acute toxicity	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/ecotox	8080
Human Inhalation Model	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/lungexposure	8080
Nanobio: a Biokinetic model for ENM distribution in freshwater ecosystems	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/nanobio	80
NanoInhale: a PBPK model for describing the biodistribution of TiO ₂ in humans after inhalation exposure	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/nanoinhale	80
Biodaph: a simple kinetic model for describing the biodistribution of different TiO ₂ ENMs in D.magna	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/biodaph	80
Deep Learning model API to run the analyses of NM exposure effects on Daphnia Magna	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/deepdaph	5000
Deep Learning models to predict NM exposure effects on Daphnia Magna	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/deepdaph-models	27017 / 8501
Deep Learning User interface to predict NM exposure effects on Daphnia Magna	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/nanosolveit/deepdaph	80
NanoImage: An automated tool for extracting descriptors from electronic images	NTUA	https://hub.docker.com/r/eucliaio/nanoimage	8080
NanoXtract: a unique online tool for the calculation of image descriptors based on TEM images of NMs	NovaM	https://hub.docker.com/r/novamechanics/nanoextract	8080
Sbpot: Model predicting median (%) strand breaks, estimated from built-in microscope image analysis tools.	NTUA, NILU	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/nanosolveit/sbpot	80

eUTOPIA - Preprocessing and analysis of omics data	UTA	https://hub.docker.com/r/grecolab/eutopia	3838
FunMappOne - Visualisation of molecular biology experiments	UTA	https://hub.docker.com/r/grecolab/funmappone	3838
Molecular Pathway database access with SPARQL queries	UM	https://hub.docker.com/r/aammar/virtuoso-httpd	8080
Adverse Outcome Pathway Wiki data access with SPARQL queries	UM	https://hub.docker.com/r/aammar/virtuoso-httpd	8080
BridgeDb	UM	https://hub.docker.com/r/bigcatu/m/bridgedb	8183
ChEMBL: protein binding info and assay data	UM	https://hub.docker.com/r/aammar/virtuoso-httpd	8080